

Differentiated Learning for Foundational Education

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Ambitious Impact (AIM) exists to increase the number and quality of effective charities improving human and animal well-being worldwide. We strive to achieve this goal through our rigorous research process and our Incubator Program, which connects talented individuals with high-impact ideas.

Our Charity Entrepreneurship Incubation Program provides potential entrepreneurs with two months of cost-covered, intensive training designed by founders for founders, along with ongoing support. Our researchers identify evidence-based, high-impact interventions and guide founders in finding co-founders to launch and scale these ideas.

Note to readers: Our research is designed for AIM decision-makers and Charity Entrepreneurship Incubation Program participants. It aims to identify the best ideas for our programs. Consequently, reports on those not recommended for incubation can often be less polished.

For questions about the content of this research, please contact Filip Murár at filip@charityentrepreneurship.com.

Differentiated learning / Summary

Description

Differentiated Learning (DL) is an educational approach that groups children by learning level, rather than their age, providing targeted instruction to improve foundational literacy and numeracy skills. This approach ensures that students who have fallen behind receive tailored instruction, allowing them to catch up on foundational skills. DL has been implemented at scale in multiple countries and evaluated by several randomized controlled trials (RCTs), making it one of the most promising interventions for improving the quality of education in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Counterfactual impact

Cost-effectiveness analysis: We estimate the cost-effectiveness of this intervention to be between \$12 and \$45 (USD) per person doubling their future income. This estimate is based on projected impacts in the Philippines, the most promising country in our geographic assessment (see [Table 2](#)). The extent of this effect depends on the assumed relationship between education improvement and income gains.¹ This meets our \$30 benchmark in most cases. Additionally, our model indicates that dozens of other countries also meet this cost-effectiveness bar (see [Section 6](#) or the [geographic assessment](#)).

Scale potential: A successful charity could operate at a large scale. If expanded to cover 10% of the Philippines, we estimate it could generate 1.6–6.2 million consumption doublings per year.

Potential for success

Robustness of evidence: We are highly confident in the effectiveness of this intervention. DL is one of the most studied education interventions in developing countries, with numerous RCTs demonstrating effectiveness (see [Section 3](#)).

¹ At AIM, we model the relationship between one standard-deviation improvement in test scores (a meaningful academic gain relative to peers) and income to be between 10% and 40%, based on [our review of the literature](#).

Theory of Change: The primary Theory of Change (ToC) is to deliver DL—likely in collaboration with the NGO Pratham—in a country where no organization is currently delivering it or where only small local actors are active in limited regions.

There are various delivery models, including:

- Training teachers to implement DL in their classrooms.
- Running short-term learning “camps” led by staff or volunteers.

It is unclear to us which model would be most effective, and the best approach may vary by country or region.

An alternative ToC would involve partnering with existing NGOs that already deliver DL, providing them with training and monitoring and evaluation (M&E) to help them scale up and improve delivery quality. This approach could allow the charity to operate even in countries where DL is already present while still having a cost-effective impact (see [Section 2](#)).

Other

Expert views: Experts from Pratham, TaRL Africa, J-PAL, and the World Bank were generally supportive of us working on DL. Some raised concerns about whether we could deliver DL to a high standard, though we suspect these concerns stem from past experiences with low-quality or uncooperative implementers—a challenge unlikely to apply to an AIM charity. Overall, key stakeholders in this space appear highly collaborative and were generally enthusiastic about the prospect of new implementing partners (see [Section 4](#)).

Implementation factors: DL is a complex intervention and evidence suggests that both uptake and fidelity of delivery strongly influence its effectiveness. While we expect the charity would be able to implement DL successfully at a small scale, we have some concerns about its ability to maintain high-quality delivery at a larger, sustainable scale (see [Section 7](#)).

Differentiated Learning / Crucial considerations

Would this charity be additional?

While DL is not being implemented at scale in many countries, major organizations are already planning expansions, raising concerns that a new charity might provide limited additional value. However, existing actors are capacity-constrained, with more funding available for DL than they can absorb. Additionally, leading organizations such as Pratham and TaRL Africa typically operate via local implementing partners, and an AIM charity could serve in this role. Finally, most experts we consulted supported the entry of new high-quality implementers.

Which exact ToC should this charity pursue?

While both a volunteer-led model (more effective but less scalable) and a teacher-led model (more scalable but less effective) are viable approaches (see [Section 3.2](#)), it is also unclear whether the charity should deliver the intervention directly or support existing NGOs in scaling up and improving delivery.

The most suitable approach may depend on the country and context, and we do not yet have strong evidence to recommend one over the other. Potential founders of this charity should conduct follow-up research and consult experts—particularly those with prior experience implementing DL and local expertise in the target country—to determine the best model.

How does DL compare with other education interventions, such as structured pedagogy?

AIM previously recommended incubating a charity to deliver Structured Pedagogy (SP), another highly studied and cost-effective education intervention, which led to the creation of the [Learning Alliance](#). This raises the question of how DL and SP compare and whether they could be synergistic. Our models suggest that both interventions have overlapping ranges of cost-effectiveness, though DL may be less cost-effective due to being more labor-intensive.

While SP focuses on improving teaching quality in standard classrooms, DL provides remedial education for students who have fallen behind. Given these distinct aims, the two approaches may be complementary, with a recent study in Morocco showing promising results from a combined approach.² In the future, this charity could explore co-delivering SP as a potential expansion.

² [Ibrahim et al. \(2024\)](#)

Contents

1	Background	5
	1.1 Introduction to the idea and problem	5
2	Theories of change	10
	2.1 Barriers	10
	2.2 Potential theories of change	11
	2.3 ToC for this charity	13
3	Quality of evidence	19
	3.1 Measuring education	19
	3.2 Evidence that DL improves learning outcomes	20
	3.3 Evidence that education quality improves lifetime earnings	22
	3.4 Evidence that education quality improves economic growth	22
	3.5 Considerations for other externalities	22
4	Expert views	24
	4.1 Notes for effective implementation	24
	4.2 Space for a new organization	26
	4.3. Complementary and alternative interventions	26
5	Geographic assessment	28
	5.1 Where existing organizations work	28
	5.2 Geographic assessment	29
6	Cost-effectiveness analysis	33
	6.1 Costs	33
	6.2 Effects	33
7	Implementation	36
	7.1 What does working on this idea look like?	36
	7.2 Key factors	36
	7.3 Remaining uncertainties	41
8	Conclusion	43
	References	44
	Appendix A: D-Prize Organizations	46

1 Background

As part of our 2024 research agenda, we explored interventions that could effectively increase beneficiaries' incomes or boost countries' economic growth.³ In this context, we investigated Differentiated Learning (DL), an evidence-based approach that tailors instruction to students' learning levels rather than their age, helping them build foundational literacy and numeracy skills.

Previously, AIM's research into cost-effective education interventions led to the incubation of [Learning Alliance](#), a charity delivering structured pedagogy. At the time, structured pedagogy was prioritized due to its relative neglectedness, making it a high-impact area for philanthropy. With DL similarly recognized as a high-impact approach, this report examines its potential to improve foundational learning in low-resource settings.

1.1 Introduction to the idea and problem

Education as an intervention area

Education as a philanthropic focus area is shaped by two competing factors. On the one hand, it consistently attracts considerable attention and resources, with many organizations working to address educational challenges worldwide. On the other hand, despite ongoing investment, the demand for effective and impactful educational interventions remains high due to persistent gaps in educational support.

In recent years, these investments have significantly improved school attendance. As shown in Figure 1, the global percentage of primary-school-age children not in school halved between 1999 and 2019.

³ To read more about our approach to selecting intervention ideas for our program, please see [Murár \(2025\)](#)

Data source: UNESCO for the year 2019
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 OurWorldinData.org – Research and data to make progress against the world's largest problems.

Figure 1: Primary school non-attendance by region (Roser, 2021).

However, learning outcomes have not kept pace with attendance gains. Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, the world was experiencing a learning crisis. *Learning poverty* (World Bank, 2021)—the inability to read and understand a simple text by age 10—affected 57% of ten-year-olds in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) and 86% in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (United Nations Statistics Division, 2023). Between 2015 and 2019, there was no reduction in global learning poverty, highlighting the need for targeted and effective interventions in education (World Bank et al., 2022). Post-pandemic, the situation has worsened, with UNESCO estimating that 90% of children in low-income countries cannot read with comprehension by the age of 10 (Azevedo et al., 2021).

The returns to education—and the consequences of its shortcomings—are both private and public. Privately, education enhances individual earning potential,

improving economic mobility for those with access to quality education. Publicly, it contributes to societal benefits such as economic growth, improved health outcomes, greater civic engagement, and lower crime rates ([World Bank, 2018](#)).

Differentiated Learning

DL is an educational approach that groups children based on learning level rather than age to provide targeted instruction to improve foundational skills in literacy and numeracy. Developed by the education NGO Pratham in India under the name *Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL)*,⁴ this method ensures that students who have fallen behind receive instruction that is tailored to their individual needs, allowing them to catch up on foundational skills. This approach addresses the widespread issue of children completing primary schooling without acquiring essential reading and arithmetic skills, which hampers their ability to meet curricular expectations and negatively affects their long-term career prospects.

DL is considered one of the “Great Buys” in education philanthropy due to its proven cost-effectiveness and has become a popular intervention ([GEAAP, 2023](#)). In an assessment of over 150 education interventions across 46 countries, [Angrist et al. \(2020\)](#) found DL to be among the most cost-effective, achieving learning gains equivalent to up to four additional years of schooling—in terms of actual knowledge gained—measured as Learning-Adjusted Years of Schooling (LAYS)⁵ per \$100 spent. Figure 2 below compares DL to other evaluated interventions.

⁴ "Teaching at the Right Level" is the term specifically coined by the NGO Pratham for this approach. It falls under the broader category of Differentiated Learning, which is also referred to as remedial education or targeted instruction.

⁵ LAYS is a holistic measure that accounts for both the quantity (years) and quality of schooling, relative to a baseline ([World Bank, 2018](#)).

Notes: Each category of education intervention shows the learning-adjusted years of school (LAYS) gained from a given intervention or policy. Each red triangle represents a cost-effectiveness estimate. The boxplot is ordered from largest to smallest mean effects, and the shaded boxplot describes the 25th and 75th percentiles. The y-axis is reported on a natural log scale.

Figure 2: Learning-Adjusted Years of School (LAYS) Gained per \$100 by education intervention category (Angrist et al., 2020).

Pratham continues to be a major implementer of DL in India while TaRL Africa—a partnership between Pratham and J-PAL⁶—has rapidly expanded across sub-Saharan Africa. Despite these successes, our discussions with Will Snider of [D-prize](#) indicated that there may still be room for additional cost-effective organizations in regions not currently covered by existing initiatives.

This need is further evidenced by the growing appetite among donors for innovative education interventions. For instance, the Global Learning [X-prize](#) has supported innovative education models, while the [D-Prize](#) explicitly funds DL-focused initiatives, offering \$20,000 grants to organizations with a vision to reach 50,000 students (about 1,000 classrooms) within five years.

⁶ J-PAL (the Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab) is a global research center based at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

While DL has many variations, this report explores the intervention as designed by Pratham and J-PAL. In this model, DL includes three core components

([Banerjee et al., 2016](#); [J-PAL, 2022](#)):

- 1. Trained implementers** – Teachers or volunteers who receive specific training in DL methods of assessment and education.
- 2. Assessment and learning materials** – DL relies on frequent, simple assessments to gauge each child's current level in subjects like literacy and numeracy. Learning materials are then tailored to match the child's ability, ensuring targeted and effective learning.
- 3. Dedicated learning time** – Time is set aside within the school day or in after-school sessions to focus exclusively on foundational skills, making DL a complementary intervention rather than a direct adjustment to existing curricula.

As outlined in more detail in [Section 2.2](#), DL can be adapted to suit the resource constraints of different environments.

The prominence of DL as an intervention shapes the focus of this report. Given the overlap between DL and structured pedagogy, as well as the success of existing organizations in implementing and scaling DL, this report frequently references AIM's [Structured Pedagogy report](#) and draws on the [approach and track record](#) of TaRL Africa as its foundation. The primary goal of this report is to analyze potential gaps in either the locations or delivery models of existing organizations to determine whether a new organization could achieve high-impact, cost-effective results in these areas.

2 Theories of change

2.1 Barriers

Despite its track record, DL has not been widely adopted as standard practice in many countries. Barriers to its adoption include the need for shifts in teacher attitudes, investment in teacher training, and buy-in from governments and policymakers to adjust rigid education systems.

Government collaboration

- **Policy priorities:** Many governments focus on school enrollment and completion rates as primary education success metrics rather than actual learning outcomes. DL's emphasis on measuring and targeting instruction based on student proficiency may seem, to some policymakers, like a departure from established priorities. Education economist and thought leader Lant Pritchett has highlighted this misalignment as a major challenge in scaling education interventions ([Pritchett, 2021](#)).
- **Government buy-in:** Several experts we interviewed also identified securing government support as key to the successful implementation of DL. If local and national governments are unwilling to prioritize education quality over school-year completion rates, this presents a notable barrier to scaling DL.

Implementation

- **Context-specific adaptation:** Effective DL implementation requires tailoring content to local languages, cultural contexts, and student needs to maximize engagement and effectiveness. This involves modifying instructional materials, incorporating relevant examples, and ensuring continuous training and support for teachers and mentors. A structured implementation process includes needs assessment, collaborative program design, pilot programs, and routine support.
- **Monitoring and support:** Sustained teacher support and monitoring are essential for DL programs to be implemented effectively. Without regular supervision and mentorship, teachers may revert to old methods—a risk

noted by [Banerjee et al., \(2016\)](#) in their evaluation of variations of this intervention.

2.2 Potential theories of change

Direct DL implementation approaches

DL broadly consists of three core components: trained implementers (teachers and/or volunteers), student assessment and learning materials, and dedicated learning time. Research suggests that all three need to be present for DL to be successfully implemented.

[Banerjee et al. \(2016\)](#) conducted a series of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in India between 2008 and 2014, testing different iterations of these components.^{7,8} The following five models illustrate the different implementation approaches tested across these experiments. For ease of reading, those highlighted in green yielded positive results while those in red did not.

- 1. Volunteer-led after-school model (Pratham's original model):** Volunteers, trained independently of school staff, led DL interventions outside the traditional curriculum. These volunteers provided target instruction separate from the formal classroom setting.
- 2. Teacher-led summer camp:** Teachers were trained in DL and provided with learning materials to implement intensive summer school programs during school holidays.
- 3. Materials-only in-class approach:** Schools received learning materials (such as books or worksheets) without any additional teacher training or support. Teachers were expected to integrate these materials into their regular teaching methods independently.

⁷ Note that, while most of the evidence on DL comes from India, at least two RCTs have also been performed in Africa; see [Section 3.2](#).

⁸ The merits of this study are discussed in more detail in [Section 3.2](#) below.

4. **Teacher training with materials:** Teachers were trained in the DL methodology and provided with learning materials, with the aim of incorporating the approach into their regular teaching during the school year.
5. **Teacher and volunteer training with materials:** Both teachers and volunteers were trained to implement DL and received materials, with volunteers working alongside teachers in classrooms

The success of the teacher-led summer camps—detailed in [Section 3.2](#)—demonstrated that **government teaching staff could effectively implement DL under certain conditions**. However, the failure of the other methods suggests strict parameters must be met for success.

[Banerjee et al. \(2016\)](#) found that when materials alone were provided, trained teachers defaulted to using textbooks prescribed for the relevant grades rather than applying DL principles. Similarly, when volunteers were placed in classrooms, they were often used by teachers as assistants to implement conventional methods rather than delivering targeted DL sessions.

Their findings reinforce that **a successful DL program requires trained implementers (teachers and/or volunteers), student assessment and learning materials, and dedicated learning time**.

Alternative Theory of Change

An alternative approach for a new organization could involve identifying and supporting existing local organizations with the potential to implement DL effectively. Rather than training teachers and delivering DL directly, the charity would focus on providing high-level monitoring, quality assurance, and ad-hoc support to promising pre-existing DL organizations. This idea emerged from an expert interview (though not with a DL practitioner) as a potentially impactful angle for a new non-profit organization.

In this ToC, ongoing monitoring and support would enable successful models to scale, embedding DL within local education systems and driving widespread

foundational learning improvements. Evidence from [Angrist and Meager \(2023\)](#) (discussed [below](#)) suggests that improved implementation fidelity—ensuring students are grouped and taught at the level recommended by the program rather than being placed in a group that is too advanced for their actual learning needs—could increase DL’s learning effects 0.22 standard deviations (SDs). This improvement is comparable to some of the more modest gains achieved by DL interventions.

While this report primarily focuses on direct DL intervention, this alternative ToC may serve as a valuable complement or even a viable alternative depending on the intervention’s context. Notably, Pratham—the leading technical partner for DL globally—is actively working to scale to new regions through local partnerships. A new organization dedicated to identifying and supporting local partners could play a critical role in facilitating this expansion.

2.3 ToC for this charity

The ToC for this charity follows a resource-informed differentiated approach.

Based on the insights detailed above, Pratham and J-PAL recommend two mainstreaming approaches depending on the resource constraints:

1. **Teacher-led model** (for well-resourced environments)
 - Government teachers are trained to implement DL within the regular school day, grouping children by learning level rather than grade for dedicated instructional periods.
 - Requires government support to allocate time within the school day for DL activities.
 - Teachers receive ongoing mentorship from "leaders of practice" who provide guidance and monitor implementation.
2. **Volunteer-led “Learning Camp” model** (for low-resource settings)

- Children are grouped by learning level for focused sessions of two to three hours per day
- Learning Camps are often held during the school day with local authorities' approval, allowing students to return to regular classes in between.
- Led by Pratham instructors, these intensive ten-day Learning Camps are repeated throughout the year, providing a total of 30-50 instructional days.

A ToC that integrates flexibility for both the teacher-led and volunteer-led models is presented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Theory of Change for this charity. Dotted boxes and lines represent secondary pathways of impact through economic growth, which are discussed further in [Section 3.3](#) below.

Each numbered circle in Figure 3 represents an assumption about the relationships between elements of the ToC. Assumptions are color-coded to indicate confidence levels: green for high confidence, yellow for mid-to-high confidence, orange for mid-level confidence, and red for low confidence.

No.	Assumption	Evidence/Explanation
1	Students are consistently present for assessments, and assessments accurately reflect their literacy and numeracy levels. (Likely)	It is assumed that student attendance for DL activities will reflect current school attendance levels. However, in "summer camp" models, attendance could be lower since participation demands extend beyond regular school attendance. Neither Pratham nor RCTs investigating this method have flagged this as a major concern.
2	Implementers are consistently present and equipped to deliver assessment materials. (Likely)	TaRL Africa has successfully implemented this model across multiple SSA countries. No indication suggests that implementer quality would significantly differ between SSA and other LMICs. A potential risk is misjudging the approach (volunteer vs. teacher) best suited to the setting. Relying on teachers in low-resource schools with high teacher absenteeism could undermine this pathway.
3	Implementers are motivated and structurally able to apply DL methods after training. (Likely)	TaRL Africa's success suggests this is achievable but depends on securing school and government buy-in to allocate dedicated instructional time. Some adapting may be necessary for different regional contexts.
4	Learning materials appropriately match students' learning needs. (Highly likely)	Pratham provides an overview of the required materials, and TaRL Africa advocates an adaptable approach developed with input from regional education professionals. Testing in pilot implementation is needed to confirm alignment with specific contexts.
5	Teachers who have received training and materials are equipped to provide DL teaching. (Highly likely)	This model was effective in an RCT setting in India (Banerjee et al., 2016), is recommended by J-PAL in some contexts, and TaRL Africa has successfully implemented it across multiple SSA countries.
6	There is sufficient political support and interest from the Ministry of Education to engage in a	This varies by country and may be difficult to predict. TaRL Africa's success suggests feasibility in some contexts, and prior track

	partnership for scaling DL. (Medium confidence)	records may aid credibility-building efforts.
7	Implementers will continue to assess and regroup students at appropriate intervals to ensure continued progress. (Highly likely)	This responsibility will be managed by the organization.
8	Tailored instruction based on learning levels will lead to improved literacy and numeracy skills. (Highly likely)	A series of RCTs and ongoing evaluations of DL interventions across various settings support the effectiveness of this approach, with observed test score increases ranging from 0.15 and 0.7 SDs. Further discussed in more Section 3.2 .
9	Trained teachers are present and motivated to provide DL teaching. (Likely)	In government teaching mainstreaming models, this risk was mitigated by establishing dedicated instructional periods for DL. However, variability in teacher commitment remains a potential challenge.
10	The government is committed to integrating DL into the national curriculum with sustainable funding and support. (Medium confidence)	This will likely be highly country specific. Some governments continue to prioritize committed to school completion rates over learning quality, which could reduce interest in this intervention.
11	Integrating DL into the government school system enhances its application across the education system. (Highly likely)	If the government commits to integrating DL into the national curriculum, implementation through teacher training has been successfully achieved in multiple contexts, including by Pratham and TaRL Africa.
12	DL intervention can be scaled consistently across the school system. (Likely)	A differentiated approach that considers varying resource constraints may facilitate scalability.
13	Foundational skills in literacy and numeracy form the basis for continued educational success and, by extension, better job opportunities. (Medium confidence)	Evidence suggests that foundational skills in literacy and numeracy support educational attainment and may improve job prospects. For example, Evans & Hares (2021) report that a 1 SD increase in numeracy skills is associated with an 18% wage increase in high-income countries. However, these findings are largely correlational and other factors such as socioeconomic background may influence outcomes. Additionally, Hanushek and Woessmann (2012) suggest that gains in basic literacy could correlate with economic growth, indirectly influencing labor market opportunities. However, these links are complex, and the extent to which

		foundational skills alone drive better job prospects can vary by context and economic conditions, including labor demand and structural factors.
14	Improved employment opportunities over students' lifetimes will result in higher income than they would have otherwise achieved without these educational interventions. (Medium confidence)	Studies such as Hanushek et al. (2016) indicate that a 1 SD increase in test scores correlates with a 10-45% earnings increase. However, these estimates are primarily based on high-income countries, and attributing causal effect is complex. Moreover, this is likely impacted by local economic conditions including labor demand.
15	Increased earnings will directly translate into higher household income and improved consumption. (Highly likely)	Income and consumption tend to be closely correlated, particularly for individuals in poverty (Meyer & Sullivan, 2003). While higher-income individuals may save or invest rather than spend, this intervention is expected to primarily benefit lower-income groups, for whom income gains are more likely to translate into increased consumption.
16	Increased income and consumption spending are correlated with improved welfare. (Highly likely)	Extensive body of literature documents a close link between income and self-reported well-being. See, for example, Ortiz-Ospina and Roser (2013) , or Section 3.3 below.

3 Quality of evidence

This section examines the evidence on the impact of DL. First, we discuss how education outcomes are measured in the literature. Next, we review the evidence on DL's effectiveness in improving learning outcomes. Finally, we explore research on the broader effects of education, including its influence on income, economic growth, and externalities.

3.1 Measuring education

As discussed in more detail in the [Structured Pedagogy \(SP\) report](#), education is commonly measured using three key approaches:

- 1. Standard Deviations (SDs) in Test Scores:** Test score improvements are often reported in standard deviations to enable cross-comparisons of interventions. A one SD increase is roughly equivalent to an additional 5.5 years of schooling.
- 2. Learning-Adjusted Years of Schooling (LAYS):** Developed by the World Bank, LAYS accounts for both schooling quantity and quality. One LAY represents the equivalent of one high-quality year of education, comparable to education in top-performing systems such as Singapore's.
- 3. Foundational Literacy and Numeracy Assessments:** Tools such as the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) and Early Grade Mathematics Assessment (EGMA) measure basic literacy and numeracy skills, offering direct insight into foundational learning levels. This World Bank aggregates these into a broader measure called "learning poverty," which tracks the proportion of children who cannot independently and fluently read a simple, short narrative at the age of 10.

Echoing the SP report, this report focuses on foundational literacy, numeracy skills and learning poverty, which are best captured through direct assessments

like EGRA or EGMA (or equivalent national assessments). This focus aligns with DL's core objective—improving foundational literacy and numeracy skills.

3.2 Evidence that DL improves learning outcomes

A strong body of evidence, including RCTs across India and at least three in sub-Saharan Africa, demonstrates the effectiveness of DL in significantly improving student learning outcomes.

- [Angrist and Meager \(2023\)](#) conducted a meta-analysis of eight RCTs—seven in India and one in Kenya—finding that DL yields an average learning gain of 0.43 SDs, with the potential gains reaching 0.85 SDs when implemented with high fidelity (i.e., students correctly grouped and taught according to their ability). Specifically, a meta-analysis of three papers covering eight studies found that volunteer-led programs saw an average improvement of 0.49 standard deviations, while teacher-led programs saw 0.24 SDs. However, nearly all of this variation appears to be explained by differences in intervention fidelity.⁹

Additionally, a new RCT in Botswana tested the impact of improved fidelity and found that more precise implementation boosted learning gains by 0.22 SDs. This suggests that ensuring high fidelity execution may further enhance DL's impact and that refining fidelity in existing DL programs could significantly improve learning outcomes.

The meta-analysis draws from [Banerjee et al. \(2007\)](#), [Banerjee et al. \(2016\)](#), and [Duflo et al., \(2011\)](#), all discussed in greater detail below. Importantly, the study found **no evidence of publication bias**, likely due the large sample sizes in the trials considered.

- [Banerjee et al. \(2007\)](#) is the foundational RCT for DL and remains a key reference in the literature despite its age. Conducted in urban India with Pratham volunteers, this study found that **DL increased average test scores**

⁹ Other factors considered included teacher attendance, student attendance, and materials usage.

by 0.28 SDs, with the most substantial gains among students who started with lower skill levels. However, these effects faded by 0.10 SDs one year later.

- [Banerjee et al. \(2016\)](#) is the most widely cited study on DL's effectiveness. It examined multiple RCTs across different DL models in northern India, with student sample sizes ranging from 8,900 to 12,576. The study assessed intensive learning camps, in-school support, and volunteer-led programs (see the [Theory of Change](#) section for details). The most substantial impact was observed in Uttar Pradesh, **where summer camps and volunteer instruction led to 0.70 SD gains in literacy and numeracy. In contrast, government mainstreaming of DL in Haryana resulted in 0.15 SD gains in language skills, while a similar initiative in Bihar yielded 0.13 SD gains in language and a 0.11 SD gains in numeracy.** These results indicate that while DL consistently improves foundational skills, the effect size varies depending on the delivery model and setting. Notably, there was no clear relationship between initial student proficiency levels and the size of gains.
- [Duflo et al. \(2013\)](#) conducted an RCT in Kenya, which found sorted students into skill-based classes **improved test scores by 0.28 SDs, compared to 0.16 SDs in non-DL classes that received alternative interventions.** Moreover, these **gains persisted one year later.**
- [Duflo et al. \(2022\)](#) conducted a four-arm RCT in Ghana, testing several DL models, including assistant-led remedial pull-out lessons, assistant-led remedial after-school lessons, assistant-led smaller class sizes, and [teacher](#)-implemented partial day tracking. Across these models, average student learning improved by 0.1 SDs but by 0.4 SDs when accounting for imperfect implementation.

Although effect sizes vary across studies, the evidence consistently supports DL's positive impact on learning outcomes. Gains tend to be more modest in government mainstreaming models but remain significant. Crucially, program fidelity—ensuring DL is implemented as designed—plays a key role in maximizing learning improvements. Some studies suggest that learning gains may fade over

time, particularly in less intensive DL models. However, the evidence on long-term persistence remains inconclusive.

3.3 Evidence that education quality improves lifetime earnings

There is a substantial body of evidence examining the link between education and earnings. We summarize this research, along with our interpretation, in [our research note on the returns to education](#).

In summary, our view is that there are considerable returns to education in terms of higher lifetime incomes, in addition to non-financial benefits. Our quantitative models (see [Section 6](#)) assume that if education quality improves such that students' standardized test scores increase by one SD, their future earnings will rise by 10–40%.

3.4 Evidence that education quality improves economic growth

Research consistently links higher education quality, particularly improvements in cognitive skills, **to economic growth.** For further details, we refer readers to our [research note on the returns to education](#).

3.5 Considerations for other externalities

The [2018 World Development Report](#) highlights positive externalities of improved education that are often overlooked in economic models. These include:

- **Enhanced health outcomes,** particularly for the children of educated parents (i.e., the next generation).

- **Reduced crime rates**, through multiple mechanisms, including higher opportunity costs of crime due to increased earning potential and reduced idle time among young people.
- **Decreased inequality**, strengthening social cohesion by equipping disadvantaged students with foundational skills that create pathways out of poverty.

Experts interviewed for this report believed that the returns to education are chronically underestimated. One expert argued that foundational learning interventions carry no negative externalities, countering concerns about job displacement by stating that this does not apply at the foundational education level.

4 Expert views

The headline takeaway across expert interviews is that there are potential opportunities for new organizations to address bottlenecks in implementation or enter underserved geographies. However, expert opinions differed on what that might entail. Common features of success behind scaling new organizations included robust government relationships, local partnerships, and a strong relationship with Pratham, which maintains a leading role in designing and safeguarding the fidelity of DL.

We conducted six interviews for this report, spanning eight experts. Due to the depth of the DL landscape, many experts had overlapping experience as researchers, implementers, and funders, allowing them to provide insight across the breadth of the report. A key emphasis of all interviews was assessing the potential for a new organization given the already well-developed DL landscape.

Table 1: Overview of interviews we conducted

Interviewee	Organization
Vadim Albinsky	Founders Pledge
Deon Filmer	World Bank
Alex Banda	TaRL Africa (Nigeria)
Catherine Botros-Odingo	TaRL Africa (HQ)
Bala Venkatachalam	Pratham USA
John Floretta, Claudia Marcías, Maddie Brancel	J-PAL

The key takeaways from the interview notes are as follows:

4.1 Notes for effective implementation

- **Essential partnership with Pratham or TaRL Africa.** Pratham, as the initiator and custodian of the DL methodology, plays a critical role in its global expansion and quality assurance. Any new organization aiming to implement DL must collaborate with Pratham from the outset—not only due to

Pratham's extensive expertise and technical support but also because of its prominence in the education landscape. Pratham has trademarked the TaRL name and methodology. Meanwhile, TaRL Africa, co-founded by Pratham and J-PAL, serves as the regional authority in SSA.

- **Government partnerships for scale and cost-effectiveness.** The most consistent narrative across expert interviews was the importance of a strong relationship with local governments and ministries of education. It is essential for both scaling the intervention and ensuring cost-effectiveness. As DL becomes mainstreamed, governments are expected to assume a greater share of its costs.

Often, schools themselves initiate partnerships by reaching out to an existing organization (i.e., Pratham or TaRL Africa) to express interest in DL. However, **expert interviews provided little insight into how successful organizations have been at generating strong government relationships independently.** Partnering with established technical organizations like J-PAL and Pratham could enhance a new organization's credibility, making it easier to secure government support.

Additionally, the presence of other educational organizations in a country should not automatically exclude it from consideration. Many existing organizations may be limited to specific regions and may not be implementing DL in direct partnership with the government.

- **Importance of contextualisation.** Adapting DL content to local languages, cultural contexts, and student needs helps ensure engagement and comprehension. This includes customizing stories and examples, as well as providing ongoing training and support for teachers and mentors. A structured implementation process should involve a needs assessment, collaborative program design, pilot programs, and routine support.

4.2 Space for a new organization

- **Funding is not the primary bottleneck for DL implementation.** Overall funding for foundational learning and numeracy is increasing. Two

interviewees suggested that more funding is available than there are cost-effective organizations ready to absorb it, particularly those demonstrating high effectiveness. Instead, a greater challenge appears to be the capacity of cost-effective organizations to scale beyond their current geographies.

- **Identifying neglected geographies.** A new organization could focus on regions where major DL implementers (Pratham and TaRL Africa) have no immediate plans to enter (see [Section 5.1](#)). While both organizations have long-term ambitions for broader coverage, certain countries remain outside their near-term strategies—possibly due to major barriers such as uncooperative governments or particularly complex education systems that could complicate implementation.
- **Supporting Pratham and TaRL Africa’s target regions.** Alternatively, a new organization could focus on regions that Pratham and TaRL Africa are considering for expansion, but with a complementary approach—identifying and existing local organizations that may need support in meeting DL standards. By facilitating partnerships between these organizations and Pratham or TaRL Africa, a new charity could help scale DL more efficiently while allowing established players to avoid direct management of local complexities.

4.3. Complementary and alternative interventions

In addition to direct advice, expert interviews highlighted several **complementary interventions** that address foundational learning and broader educational support. These are summarized below.

Relationship to DL	Intervention
To be implemented alongside DL	Structured pedagogy: likely to work well in combination with DL. ¹⁰

¹⁰ A recent study showed that the co-implementation of targeted remediation and structured pedagogy in Morocco resulted in an educational gain of 0.90 SD ([Ibrahim et al., 2024](#)).

Relationship to DL	Intervention
Alternative iterations of DL	<p>Optimizing education in fragile states and conflict zones: supporting disrupted education systems by integrating DL into humanitarian interventions (e.g., learning in refugee camps).</p> <p>Numeracy-focused pedagogy: a potentially more targeted approach than general DL that emphasizes structured methods for improving foundational numeracy skills.</p>
An enabler of DL	<p>Changing citizen–state relationships regarding education: developing tools to support citizens in engaging with and holding governments accountable for educational quality, fostering stronger public demand for effective schooling.</p>
Education interventions that are more neglected than DL but likely still high-impact	<p>Educational awareness campaigns: initiatives aimed at increasing public understanding of the benefits of education, potentially driving greater support and engagement in learning outcomes.</p> <p>Early Childhood Development (ECD): programs focusing on early learning, such as play-based education. Interventions like BRAC’s Play Labs have demonstrated strong foundational impacts on long-term learning.</p> <p>Parental engagement and support: encouraging parental involvement in their children’s education, particularly in fostering literacy and numeracy at home.</p> <p>Psycho-social support: addressing students’ mental and emotional well-being, which is often overlooked but critical for effective learning.</p>

5 Geographic assessment

This section reviews the current DL landscape and presents an in-depth analysis to identify countries with the highest potential for a new organization's involvement.

5.1 Where existing organizations work

The major organizations implementing DL at or near government mainstreaming scale are TaRL Africa, Pratham, and Youth Impact.

- Pratham is fully operational in multiple regions in India and has near-term expansion plans for Latin America and North Africa, with longer-term ambitions for Southeast Asia and the Middle East.
- TaRL Africa is fully operational in three countries, collaborates with partner organizations in 11 additional countries as a technical partner, and has near-future expansion plans in three more. These partnerships involve program supervision through regular check-ins and providing targeted support when needed. While the extent and effectiveness of each partnerships may vary, this report does not differentiate them due to time constraints. TaRL Africa's long-term strategy envisions expansion across all of SSA.
- Youth Impact, co-founded by Noam Angrist of the [What Works Hub](#) and the University of Oxford, is active in Botswana.

Additionally, D-Prize has launched a funding round to support new organizations in this space, providing grants to 11 organizations across Africa. However, these grants are relatively small,¹¹ and assessing the current scale and impact of these new organizations remains challenging. A full list and high-level details of these organizations are in Appendix A. Of these D-Prize-supported organizations, only

¹¹The prize offers \$20,000 to teams that can create a new organization that teaches the TaRL education program to students who otherwise would fall behind. Winning organizations are required to present a vision to reach 50,000 students (about 1,000 classrooms) within five years. It is unclear from the website which organizations have successfully reached that target.

one—based in Nigeria (where TaRL Africa is also highly active) —appears to be working directly with the government.

J-PAL has identified additional DL organizations operating in several countries, though not all are explicitly named ([J-PAL, 2022](#)). Countries with DL presence beyond Pratham and TaRL Africa presence are highlighted in blue in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Existing Pratham and TaRL Africa organization presence.

5.2 Geographic assessment

We conducted a [weighted factor geographic assessment model](#) to identify countries where a new organization could have the greatest potential impact.

The model incorporates the following factors:

1. **Baseline educational outcomes:** estimated using learning deprivation, which measures the share of children completing primary school who do

not meet minimum proficiency levels in literacy and numeracy. It therefore directly reflects the challenge that DL seeks to address. This metric, defined by the [Global Alliance to Monitor Learning](#) (GAML) under the SDG 4.1.1 monitoring framework, provides a standardized, cross-country approach.

- 2. Potential reach:** estimated using the size of the population attending primary school. Specifically, we multiplied the total 5–14 year-old population of each country by the percentage of children in this age group attending school at any level. Where data was missing, we imputed values using regional averages for consistency.
- 3. Economic need:** The economic need for an income- and growth-promoting intervention was captured by GDP per capita.
- 4. Neglectedness:** We [mapped the presence](#) of the three largest DL implementers (Pratham, Youth Impact, and TaRL Africa) and assigned scores based on their level of involvement in each country:
 - 3 points: Organization supports a government-led DH program.
 - 2 points: Organization supports a partner-led program.
 - 1 point: Organization has explicit plans to expand into this country in the near future.
 - 0.5 point: Organization is interested in this country.
 - 0 points: No indication of the organization's current or planned presence.

While other DL-style organizations are operating globally, our assumption at the time of writing this report—supported by insights from two expert interviews—is that none operate at a scale significant enough to exclude a country from our consideration based on their presence. A new organization should verify this assumption before launching in a given country.

- 5. Tractability:** assessed using two indicators:

- [Fragile States Index, 2022](#) measures political stability, governance, and corruption. Higher fragility signals greater implementation challenges.
- [Elite Consultation Scores, 2023](#) (based on expert estimates at [V-Dem](#)) captures the extent to which government leaders consult with political, social, and business elites on policy decisions. Higher consultation scores indicate a more collaborative policy environment, which is essential for successfully scaling DL within national education systems.

We calculated the z-score¹² for all these factors for each country and combined them using a weighted average to determine the most promising countries for a new DL organization (see Table 2).¹³

- Educational outcomes and potential reach—factors linked to the potential scale of impact—received the highest combined weighting at 55%.
- Neglectedness was weighted at 25%, reflecting the importance of targeting underserved regions.
- Tractability (ease of implementation) was weighted at 20%, recognizing the role of governance and stability in program success.

While scale-related factors carried the most weight, neglectedness and tractability played a relatively larger role in this assessment compared to other AIM intervention reports. This reflects their importance in determining whether a new organization can effectively enter and operate in a given country.

Based on these factors and weightings, our geographic assessment suggests that **Southeast Asia, SSA and the Central America & Caribbean (CAm & Carib) region may offer strong opportunities.** However, this model is intended as a preliminary guide, and potential charity founders should do conduct further research to confirm the most promising target countries.

¹² Z-scores represent how far a country's score deviates from the average, expressed in standard deviations.

¹³ The school population variable was log transformed to account for its wide variation across countries. Without this transformation, all but the largest values would have received z-scores near 0.

Table 2: Geographic prioritization (summary of the top 15 countries)

Country	Region	School population (age 5-14, log)	Learning depriv.	GDP/capita (USD)	Other org presence	Elite consult	FSI
Weight		10%	30%	15%	15%	10%	10%
Philippines	SE Asia	7.39	90.40	3,499	0.00	0.93	75.10
Cape Verde	SSA	6.27	89.00	3,884	0.00	0.74	57.20
Laos	SE Asia	6.79	97.50	2,054	0.00	-0.22	73.80
Dominican Republic	CAm & Carib	6.30	76.30	10,111	0.00	1.05	60.20
Ethiopia	SSA	7.34	88.70	1,027	0.50	0.65	98.10
Cambodia	SE Asia	6.37	89.00	1,760	0.00	-0.35	78.60
Indonesia	SE Asia	7.65	49.40	4,788	0.00	1.55	63.70
Pakistan	S Asia	7.63	75.00	1,589	0.00	0.22	91.70
Guatemala	CAm & Carib	6.54	75.90	5,473	0.00	-0.06	74.90
The Gambia	SSA	6.27	76.24	803	0.00	0.83	76.10
Nicaragua	CAm & Carib	6.13	78.10	2,252	0.00	-1.77	76.70
Burundi	SSA	6.50	95.50	259	0.50	-0.59	92.60
Brazil	S America	7.47	45.60	9,065	0.00	2.84	70.30
Tanzania	SSA	7.23	76.24	1,193	0.50	1.11	75.70
Honduras	CAm & Carib	6.23	74.30	3,012	0.50	0.98	78.10

We also estimated the cost-effectiveness of DL in each country, with results available in the [Geographic Assessment tab](#). Overall, we find that this intervention would be more cost-effective in lower-income countries, as DL is labor-intensive and lower staff salaries would reduce costs. However, our model currently only adjusts variable costs by country. Other cost components should ideally vary as well. For instance, the income-sharing multiplier—based on the number of family members likely to benefit from the intervention—is currently held constant using data from the Philippines but would likely be higher in SSA.

Since this was a late addition, cost-effectiveness was not incorporated into the weighted factor model. However, we encourage future researchers or potential charity founders to refine the model by integrating this data.

6 Cost-effectiveness analysis

We estimate that a DL program in the Philippines could achieve a cost-effectiveness of \$12–45 (USD) per consumption doubling. The details of our cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) are outlined below, with the full model accessible [here](#).

6.1 Costs

We categorize the fixed and variable costs for the charity as follows:

- **Fixed charity costs:** \$130,000 in the first year and \$280,000 in subsequent years. These estimates remain constant across all our CEA models.
- **Additional core staff costs:** We assume the need for three additional local staff members, with annual costs estimated at \$23,472.
- **Cost of DL per child:** We rely on estimates from [Angrist et al. \(2023\)](#), who reported an average cost of \$6.89 per child in low-income countries and \$23.43 in lower-middle-income countries. We then estimate costs for specific countries by adjusting these figures based on GDP per capita, assuming a linear relationship between income levels and program costs.

6.2 Effects

The main effect we modeled in our CEA is increased later-life income. Other potential benefits—such as improved health outcomes, higher civic engagement, and reduced crime—are not included but represent significant positive externalities that further strengthen the case for investments in education.

To calculate the benefits, we used the following inputs:

- **Reach of the charity:** We estimate that the charity could reach 10% of the school-aged population in the Philippines. This is a highly uncertain input

that could under- or over-estimate the potential reach. However, this assumption has minimal impact on cost-effectiveness, as the model is largely driven by variable costs.

- **Effect of DL on test scores:** Based on the findings in [Section 3.2](#), we estimate that DL increases test scores by 0.37 SDs. This is based on an equal-weighted average of teacher-delivered programs (0.24 SD) and volunteer-led programs (0.49 SD), as we are uncertain which model is more appropriate for the target country. To account for potential implementation fidelity and imperfect uptake, we apply validity adjustments, resulting in a final estimate of 0.23 SDs.
- **Relationship between educational improvements and income gains:** As described in our [research note on the return to education](#), we model two possible scenarios: a pessimistic scenario, assuming a 10% increase in income per 1 SD improvement in standardized test scores; and an optimistic scenario, assuming a 40% increase in income per 1 SD improvement.
- **Probability of success and counterfactual adjustments:** Following AIM's standards of modeling the cost-effectiveness of direct-delivery interventions, we assume a 100% probability of success and a 0% probability that change happens anyway. This ensures that the model directly captures the program's cost-effectiveness—that is, how inputs (costs) translate into outputs (income gains)—conditional on success. We believe this aligns with most readers' expectations when interpreting cost-effectiveness estimates.¹⁴
- **Multiplier for resource sharing:** We follow [GiveWell's \(2023\)](#)¹⁵ in adjusting benefits based on the number of individuals who might share in the increased income. This reflects household size and dependency structures.

¹⁴ We generally apply a lower probability of success only when an intervention's ultimate impact relies heavily on the actions of other actors (e.g. in cases of advocating for government policy changes). Similarly, we adjust for the probability that that change may happen anyway only when there is a realistic chance that the intervention's outcomes could occur without the involvement of this charity or an equivalent actor. Given the complexity of delivering DL with high fidelity and impact, we consider it unlikely that a country would successfully implement it at scale without significant external support. In other words, for this change to occur, charitable resources will almost certainly need to be spent—whether by this or another organization. As such, we do not apply a nonzero probability for this change to happen anyway.

¹⁵ See the note on cell A25.

Specifically, we base this multiplier on projected fertility rates in the Philippines in 2055, which we roughly estimate at 1.90.

We then assumed that a typical beneficiary of this intervention would begin experiencing its benefits nine years after participation (i.e., upon entering the workforce) and that these benefits would last for 45 years—the estimated length of a typical working life). Lastly, we assumed that this charity would take eight years to reach full scale, after which it would continue to operate indefinitely. To account for the time value of money, future costs and benefits were discounted at a rate of 4% per year, and the final result was calculated based on the present value of all discounted costs and benefits.

There are various reasons why our estimate could under- or overestimate the cost-effectiveness of this charity, including:

- The future relationship between educational attainment and income gains differing from past trends.
- The exclusion of non-economic benefits and positive externalities of education (see [Section 3.5](#)).
- Potential inaccuracies in the assumed relationship between GDP per capita and staff costs.
- Misestimation of the relative effectiveness of teacher-led and volunteer-led programs.
- Future increases in intervention costs due to rising staff salaries.
- Deviations in future household sizes from our assumptions.

Given these uncertainties, our estimate should be considered preliminary. We strongly encourage potential charity founders to refine and update the model's inputs using new country-specific data.

7 Implementation

7.1 What does working on this idea look like?

Running a DL organization requires strong relationships with both technical partners (primarily Pratham) as well as local governments. This involves actively engaging with education systems and working closely with schools, policymakers and community organizations to integrate DL into existing structures. Staying deeply connected to the local context is essential for tailoring DL to specific curriculum needs, language diversity, and cultural factors.

A second core component is capacity building and continuous monitoring. Delivering DL effectively relies on training and supporting teachers, volunteers, and mentors. Establishing a pipeline of local trainers and supervisors is crucial to sustaining and scaling the intervention, ensuring that skills and knowledge remain embedded within the education system.

7.2 Key factors

This section outlines our level of concern associated with different factors that could impact the success of a new DL charity.

Table 3: Implementation concerns

Factor	Level of concern
Talent	Low concern
Access to information	Low concern
Access to relevant stakeholders	Moderate concern
Feedback loops	Moderate concern

Funding	Low concern
Neglectedness	Moderate concern
Execution difficulty / Tractability	Low concern
Complexity of scaling	Moderate concern
Risk of harm	Low concern

Talent

Finding qualified talent for this work should not be particularly challenging.

Introducing DL into schools is not overly complex; however, delivering it at scale and with high fidelity requires careful program design and an emphasis on measurement and evaluation. Existing organizations have built up a substantial body of case studies and implementation experience that a new charity could draw upon, along with numerous resources available for developing high-quality lesson plans.

A strong co-founder for a DL charity would ideally have excellent relationship-building skills to engage governments and key stakeholders, ensuring the intervention aligns with local needs and priorities. While experience in education systems or policy work can be beneficial, the most important qualities are adaptability, a commitment to refining the DL methodology, and the ability to foster partnerships. A strong background or keen interest in developing teacher training programs would also be valuable. Above all, the right leader should be flexible, innovative, and prepared to navigate the complexities of implementing and scaling DL interventions.

Access

Information

Access to information is unlikely to be a barrier. Data on education quality, school attendance (for both students and teachers), and other relevant metrics are generally accessible, though some datasets may be outdated. Information about the DL methodology is also widely available online. If the new founder intends to build directly on Pratham's methodology, this should be feasible through relationship-building, as recommended.

For country prioritization, however, some key factors remain difficult to assess through desk research. These include government interest in DL, openness to collaboration, and the presence of existing educational initiatives that align with or complement DL. Direct engagement with local stakeholders—such as educational officials, community leaders, and NGOs—will be essential to gathering this information and ensuring an informed country selection process.

Relevant stakeholders

Establishing a strong partnership with Pratham, the core technical partner for DL globally, is essential. Their extensive expertise and proven methodology offer invaluable support, though their approach to maintaining fidelity to the model will require careful navigation. Rather than a constraint, this presents an opportunity to collaborate closely with Pratham while demonstrating adaptability and commitment to high-quality implementation.

Equally important is building partnerships with government stakeholders. Unlike the Structured Pedagogy report, this report recognizes that securing government buy-in may be more challenging than initially anticipated. Gaining trust and aligning with government priorities will take time but is critical for long-term, systemic impact.

In contrast, **identifying in-country partners—such as NGOs or community-based organizations—should be more straightforward.** DL is a well-known methodology

and, even where it is unfamiliar, local organizations working in education are likely to be open to collaboration.

Feedback loops

We expect this intervention to have moderately good feedback loops, by which we mean being able to observe that the intervention is being taken up and having an impact on intermediate outcomes (i.e., test scores). We do not expect this charity to be able to measure the ultimate impact, i.e. higher earnings.

While uptake and the fidelity of delivery are easily observable, and administering tests to students should be straightforward, this charity may face challenges aligning its work with the academic calendar. For example, it may need to wait until the next academic year to launch the intervention. Similarly, student assessments might only be possible at the end of the school year, delaying feedback on program effectiveness.¹⁶

Funding

Funding from funders in the AIM network

Founders Pledge's Global Health and Development Fund has given \$25,000 to TaRL Africa ([Founders Pledge, n.d.](#)). Given their interest in education, research, and DL support, they may be open to supporting an additional organization in this space capable of achieving comparable cost-effectiveness. This possibility was loosely discussed during expert interviews.

GiveWell has previously researched education in developing countries but deprioritized further work in this area based on its assessment of the evidence base. While GiveWell has stated it may consider funding individual education interventions in the future, it appears unlikely to fund a new education charity at this time ([GiveWell, 2018](#)).

Open Philanthropy does not seem to have researched education or given any funding to education charities.

¹⁶ The timing of assessments will depend on the charity's evaluation strategy. A pre/post design allows for testing at any point in the year. However, to measure effectiveness by comparing student progress across academic years, assessments may need to follow a 12-month cycle.

Broader funding sources

Our assessment of broader funding opportunities is primarily based on Founders Pledge's cause area report on education ([Calvert, 2019](#)):

- The World Bank and other multilateral institutions: \$4 billion annually
- International aid programs (e.g., USAID and the UK's Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office): \$8 billion annually
- [D-Prize](#): provides \$20,000 annually to DL organizations aiming to reach 50,000 students (approximately 1,000 classrooms) within five years
- [Global Innovation Fund](#): has awarded grants to multiple education organizations, with funding amounts ranging from \$300,000 to \$2.7 million
- [Co-Impact](#): offers large, long-term, flexible grants (typically \$5–20 million over five to six years) for organizations working to improve education, health, and economic opportunities in Africa, Asia, and Latin America.

Neglectedness

This intervention already receives considerable attention from funders and established organizations, particularly Pratham and TaRL Africa, both of which operate at an international scale. While DL is not an overlooked intervention, our [geographic assessment](#) suggests that Southeast Asia, South Asia (excluding India), Central America or the Caribbean remain promising regions for expansion.

Additionally, after thoughtful consideration and consultations with existing implementers, there may be select countries in SSA where implementation challenges may have deterred existing organizations, yet a new, high-quality implementer could provide significant added value.

Tractability

Given the widespread adoption of DL and the potential support from experienced technical partners, we do not expect tractability to pose a significant challenge beyond establishing government partnerships.

Complexity of scaling

Scaling DL cost-effectively hinges on strong collaboration with governments. Establishing trust and aligning priorities from the outset is critical to ensuring long-term success.

To maintain fidelity at scale, the intervention should be co-designed to ensure alignment with local education systems. This process should also include capacity-building efforts to equip stakeholders with the necessary skills and resources for successful implementation.

Risk of harm

We do not anticipate any notable risks to either founders or beneficiaries.

7.3 Remaining uncertainties

Is there more impact to be had by acting as an intermediary for Pratham in Latin America?

As discussed in [Section 2.2](#), an alternative approach for a new DL organization would be to focus on identifying and upskilling existing education charities to improve their fidelity. This model could involve directly leading the upskilling process or, alternatively, operating in a leaner capacity by acting as a connector—facilitating partnerships between local implementers and Pratham.

One study discussed in [Section 3.2](#) highlighted that improving the fidelity of a functional but low-fidelity organization could yield learning gains of 0.22 SD, potentially at a lower cost than launching a fully independent DL initiative. However, this alternative approach was not a core focus of our research, and additional investigation would be needed to assess whether it offers a more promising path than launching a direct implementation charity.

Should DL be paired with other education interventions (e.g., structured pedagogy)?

There may be potential for complementary effects between DL and other education interventions, such as structured pedagogy. While DL focuses on tailoring instruction to students' learning levels, structured pedagogy improves overall teaching quality through better lesson planning, teacher training, and instructional materials. Pairing these approaches could enhance both foundational skills and broader classroom effectiveness.

However, based on the research conducted for this report, it remains unclear whether such combinations leads to greater impact, sustainability, and scalability compared to implementing DL alone.

8 Conclusion

Overall, we find DL to be a highly promising methodology with strong evidence of improved learning outcomes, particularly for children who have fallen behind. These gains translate into meaningful long-term benefits, including better employment opportunities and higher lifetime earnings. **However, selecting a suitable country for implementation is crucial**—not only to avoid replicating the efforts of major existing organizations but also to ensure strong government partnerships that enable sustainable scaling.

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Appendix A: D-Prize Organizations

Table A1: High-level summary of DL organizations funded by D-Prize

Organization	Country	Date Founded	Size
Teach Me Well Ghana	Ghana (Bia West district)	2023	Pilot with 350 learners; Goal of 100,000 learners in the next five years
Solid Foundations Academy	Ghana (Volta region)	2023	Four public basic schools reached during pilot
Renewed Literacy and Youth Center	Uganda (Mayuge District)	2023	300 learners during the pilot
Bringing DL to Villages	Nigeria (Oyo State)	2023	300 learners during the pilot
Aloha Foundation	Uganda	2022	350 learners during pilot
Education Empowerment for Rural and Urban Slums	Kenya	2021	12,000 by 2023 (unclear if achieved)
Soma Organization	Rwanda	2021	250 students
Shopner Bhubon Education	Bangladesh (Gaibandha)	2021	10 schools
Soma Sawa	Kenya	2020	Goal was 50,000 by 2023, unclear if reached, <i>website is a deadlink</i>
LAICU <i>working with the local government</i>	Nigeria (Riyom)	2020	Goal of 5,000 learners by 2022, <i>website is a deadlink</i>
Teaching at the Right Level Namibia <i>possibly affiliated with TaRL Africa</i>	Namibia	2020	Unclear

Source: [D-Prize](#) and respective organization websites where available